

The Influence of Store Atmosphere and Sales Promotion on Customer Satisfaction and its Impact on Customer Loyalty Coffee Shop Kopilogi

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of store atmosphere and sales promotion on customer satisfaction and its impact on customer loyalty of the Kopilogi coffee shop. The survey was conducted on consumers of the Coffee Shop Kopilogi Garut, the research method used was descriptive and verification method with a total sample of 94 respondents, the data analysis used was path analysis. The results of the study show that in structure I there is an influence of store atmosphere and sales promotion on customer satisfaction by 52.7%. In structure II there is an influence of store atmosphere and sales promotion on loyalty through customer satisfaction of 76.0%.

KEYWORDS : Store Atmosphere, sales promotion, customer satisfaction, Customer loyalty

INTRODUCTION

Industry food and Drink is experienced industry _ most significant development in various parts of the world, p This can be seen by the number of perpetrators business open and develop business culinary. West Java Province is known as Provinces that have interesting cities and districts. One of them is Garut Regency which is nicknamed as Dodol City which describes having _ superiority in the field tour culinary. Tour This culinary delight is supported by many places food and center snacks , one of which is the many coffee shops in Garut Regency that offer them various type coffee products . Following there is development *coffee shop* in Garut City from 2018 to 2022:

Table 1. Development *coffee shop* Garut City

Year	Amount <i>Coffee shop</i>	percentage increase
2018	167	16%
2019	173	16%
2020	203	19%
2021	228	21%
2022	298	28%

Source : opendata.jabarprov.go.id

Table 1 shows there is enhancement amount *coffee shop* on each the year , p This indicates that competition business *coffee shops* in Garut City are getting tighter , growing amount coffee shops in an area can cause increasingly high competition in the industry . Very diverse choices demand _ consumer become more be careful in deciding his choice For do purchase.

Table 2. Some businesses Similar *coffee shop* in Garut City

No	Name <i>Coffee shop</i>	Address
1.	Gulapadi	Jl. Bank aside
2.	Two Color Coffee	Jl. Mandalagiri
3.	Lamansua Coffee	Jl. Ciledug No. 116
4.	Jemma Coffee	Jl. Veteran No. 18
5.	Warkop Bogar	Jl. Memories No. 17

Source : Google

Table 2 shows a number of a similar *coffee shop* in the Garut City area competitor for *coffee shop* Kopilogi, quite competition strict this demand Copyology for increase more strategies to be able to do it maintain his business. Strategies used in dealing with High competition is strategy oriented to consumers, this strategy is type focused marketing _ to satisfaction and desire consumer.

Table 3. Some perceived complaints consumer Garut Copyology

No	Complaint
1	Less space _ wide
2	Distance between adjacent table _
3	Not enough room organized
4	Seldom exists piece price /promo

Source : Copyology , 2023

Table 3 shows a number of complaint consumer *coffee shop* Kopilogi which indicates that satisfaction consumers on *coffee shop* Kopilogi are in the category not enough satisfaction, contentment consumer is matter important for sustainability life something company and necessary the company pays attention to customers don't feel disappointed, with its complaint Copyology need do evaluation to all things related to desires and hopes _ consumer. Satisfaction consumer arises from comparison perceived performance (outcome) against _ their expectations (Kotler & Keller, 2018) .

Satisfaction consumer is one of the causes of its formation loyalty, loyalty consumer tightly influenced by ability company for fulfil expectations and satisfaction consumer. Satisfied consumers _ Of course will own loyalty However, loyal consumers have not Of course own satisfaction.

Based on results survey preliminary work done to 30 respondents about a statement of satisfaction with the services provided Copyology the result showing as many as 63.3% said consumer not enough satisfied to Copyology and on statements will return visit Copyology the result showing as many as 36.7% stated that consumers less loyal to Copyology, so you can concluded that satisfaction and loyalty consumer *coffee shop* Kopilogi in categories not good or still very low.

Based on phenomenon research shows _ low satisfaction and loyalty consumer to Kopilogi *coffee shop*, conducted a preliminary survey to 30 respondents consumer Copyology about mix marketing. Satisfaction consumer can influenced by mix marketing , mix The marketing consists of from product (*product*), price (*price*), place (*place*), promotion (*promotion*) , people , process and *evidence* physical (*physical evidence*) (Sunarsi, 2020) .

Based on results study introduction factor affecting _ satisfaction and loyalty , namely *physical evidence* as many as 63.3% of respondents state not enough agree to *design layout* and facilities Kopilogi provides comfort and want linger at Kopilogi . Whereas as many as 23.3% said agree to *design layout* and facilities Kopilogi provides comfort. Whereas other influencing factors namely on variables promotion, namely as many as 70 % of respondents state not enough agree to statement Copyology often do promotion. So based on this data you can concluded problems faced by the Kopilogi *coffee shop* refers to variables promotion (*promotion*) and variables means physique (*physical evidence*).

Atmosphere shop (*store atmosphere*) is good triggering loyalty consumers, *store atmosphere* has all the elements influential to atmosphere shop you want created. Designed *store atmosphere* like that appearance make consumers _ become comfortable and decisive image from a shop. Promotion done For increase salesm get customer new and maintain loyalty customers and form image company. Research conducted by (Bayu, 2018) stated that satisfaction customer influenced by promotions sales , more and more promotions sales then will increase satisfaction customers , according to Popo Suryana & Haryadi (2019) stated that *store atmosphere* influential bigger than _ promotion to satisfaction customer .

Based on phenomenon that has been presented, then the formula problems in research this is:

1. How response consumer about *store atmosphere* at the Kopilogi *coffee shop*.
2. How response consumer about *sales promotion* at the Kopilogi *coffee shop*.
3. How response consumer about satisfaction at the Kopilogi *coffee shop*.
4. How response consumer about loyalty to the Kopilogi *coffee shop*.
5. How much influence *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* towards satisfaction customer *coffee shop* Kopilogi.
6. How big is the influence of *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* on satisfaction customers and their impact on loyalty good

customer _ simultaneous nor Partial.

METHOD

Methods used in research this is a method quantitative approach _ descriptive and verification, namely *path analysis*. Population in research these are consumers who have visit to *coffee shop* Kopilogi, with samples obtained totaling 94 respondents. The sampling technique used is *nonprobability sampling*. Data collection techniques by distributing questionnaire and methods coerlation used _ *pearson product moment* for test validity instruments and reliability tests use method *Cronbach's alpha*.

RESULTS

Results of validity tests carried out on variables *store atmosphere*, *sales promotion*, satisfaction customers and loyalty customers by using 25 statement items all declared valid. Because r_{counts} which is obtained greater than _ r_{table} of 0.30. Reliability test results using method *Cronbach's alpha* obtained mark coefficient reliability greater than _ r_{table} of 0.70. Because of the results from validity and reliability tests declared valid and reliable, then the questionnaire laya for used.

Table 4. Coefficient Determination Simultaneous Structure I

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.726 ^a	.527	.516	.56775

a. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source : Data processing , 2023

Coefficient correlation multiple (R) in structure I of 0.726 indicates that s _ _ simultaneous *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* have a strong relationship with satisfaction customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. Then mark coefficient determination (R Square) of 0.527 indicates that in general simultaneous *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* m provided a contribution (influence) of 52.7% to customer satisfaction at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. Meanwhile, the rest amounting to 47.3% is influence other outside factors *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion*.

Table 5. Coefficient Determination Partial Structure I

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Standardized Coefficients	Correlations
		Beta	Zero-order
1	X1	.412	.573
	X2	.473	.613

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source : Data processing , 2023

Based on Table 5, it can be is known influence coefficient determination in a way Partial *store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* to customer satisfaction, namely as following:

- *store atmosphere* on customer satisfaction : $0.412 \times 0.573 = 0.236$ (23.6%)
- *sales promotion* on customer satisfaction : $0.473 \times 0.613 = 0.291$ (29.1%)

Visually path diagram for structure I, depicted as following:

Figure I. Structure Path Diagram I

Use analysis path in research for take into account exists influence direct or not direct. Influence directly on the structure of the I *store atmosphere* towards satisfaction customer by 17%, meanwhile for influence No direct by 6.6%. Wading direct *sales promotion* towards satisfaction customer of 22.5% and influence No directly as much as 4 6.6%. With total influence direct or not directly on structure I amounted to 52.7% (Table 6)

Table 6. Recapitulation Influence Direct and Indirect Structure I

Variable	Path Coefficient	Influence		Total
		Direct	Indirect _ X ₁ X ₂	
<i>Store Atmosphere</i>	0.412	0.170	0.066	0.236 (23.6%)
<i>Sales promotion</i>	0.473	0.225	0.066	0.291 (29.1)
Total				0.527 (52.7%)

Table 7. Coefficient Determination Simultaneous Structure II

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.872 ^a	.760	.752	.38892

a. Predictors: (Constant), Y, X₁, X₂

b. Dependent Variable: Z

Source : Data processing , 2023

Coefficient correlation multiple (R) of 0.872 can It is known that *store atmosphere*, *sales promotion*, and customer satisfaction simultaneous have a very strong relationship with customer loyalty at the Garut Kopilogy *Coffee Shop*. Then mark coefficient determination (R Square) of 0.760 indicates that *store atmosphere* , *sales promotion* , and customer satisfaction provide a contribution (influence) of 76.0 % to customer loyalty at the Garut Kopilogy *Coffee Shop* . The rest amounting to 24.0% is influence other outside factors *store atmosphere*, *sales promotion*, and customer satisfaction.

Table 8. Coefficient Determination Partial Structure II

		Coefficients ^a	
		Standardized Coefficients	Correlations
Model		Beta	Zero-order
1	X1	.224	.628
	X2	.205	.639
	Y	.583	.838

a. Dependent Variable: Z

Source : Data processing , 2023

Based on Table 8, it can be is known influence coefficient determination in a way partial on structure II as following:

- *store atmosphere* to loyalty customers : $0.224 \times 0.628 = 0.140$ (14.0%)
- *store atmosphere* to loyalty customers : $0.205 \times 0.639 = 0.131$ (13.1%)
- influence satisfaction to loyalty customers : $0.583 \times 0.838 = 0.489$ (48.9%).

Visually path diagram for structure II, depicted as following:

Structure Path Diagram II

Influence direct or not directly on the structure II, influence direct *store atmosphere* towards loyalty customer of 0.412, influence direct *sales promotion* towards loyalty of 0.473, influence loyalty to loyalty of 0.583. Influence No direct *store atmosphere* to loyalty through satisfaction customer of 0.240, influence No direct *sales promotion* towards loyalty through satisfaction customer of 0.276. (Table 9)

Table 9. Recapitulation Influence Direct and Indirect Structure II

Variable	Influence Direct	Total Effect _{ZYX₁}	Indirect _{ZYX₂}	Total Influence
Store Atmosphere	0.412	0.240		0.652
Sales promotion	0.473		0.276	0.479
Satisfaction Customer	0.583			
Total				1,131

DISCUSSION

Influence Store Atmosphere against Satisfaction Customer

Store atmosphere or atmosphere shop is characteristics physical design _ For consumers to feel comfortable and able influence consumer in a way direct For do purchase. Structuring atmosphere environment A good shop is very important in influencing satisfaction consumer. Where is the satisfaction consumer is level one's feelings after compare perceived (performance or results) compared to expectations.

Analysis results path shows that *store atmosphere* influential significant to satisfaction customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. *Store atmosphere* makes an impact amounting to 23.6% against satisfaction customer. Coefficient track marked positive indicates that it is getting more interesting *store atmosphere* will make satisfaction customer *Coffee Shop Garut's copyology* is getting higher . Research result This in line with research previously done _ (Vriska et al., 2021) which was carried out at the *Coffee Shop Steps* , from Hypothesis test results (t test) *Store atmosphere* has an influence positive and significant to satisfaction consumer . Coefficient regression b_1 (*Store atmosphere*) is 0.287 or 28.7%, indicating that it is increasing *Store atmosphere* then it will increase satisfaction at Step *Coffee Shop*. Then strengthened by the research conducted (Anderson & Sin, 2020) results study showing there is influence significant between *Store atmosphere* towards satisfaction consumer.

Influence Sales Promotion to Satisfaction Customer

Promotion sale is one of element mix marketing that can increase sale company. Promotion sale related to influence attitudes and preferences consumers in choosing product something company. With promotions sales obtained _ consumer will feel gained profit so you can create satisfaction consumer.

Analysis results path shows that *sales promotion* influential significant to satisfaction customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. *Sales promotion* exert influence of 29.1% against satisfaction customer. Coefficient track marked positive indicates that it is getting more interesting *sales promotion* will make satisfaction customer *Coffee Shop Copyology Garut* is getting higher. Research result This in line with research previously conducted by (Adriansyah & Saputri, 2020) results research shows that *sales promotion* own influence significant to satisfaction customers, *sales promotions* have an influence of 9.3% against satisfaction customer Furthermore research conducted _ (Sutrisno & Didit, 2022) results research on variable t tests promotion sales value obtained _ No exceed value 0.05 which is significant there is influence real variable promotion sales influence and shape_ satisfaction customer.

Influence Store Atmosphere against Loyalty Customer

Store Atmosphere (atmosphere shop) has objective for develop image shop, interesting customer for visit store and provide a sense of comfort in the store. When customers have felt it comfort moment is at in the shop, feel satisfaction, happiness with the atmosphere in the shop for visitors will trust the place, so visitors be loyal to the shop. Analysis results path shows that *store atmosphere* influential significant to loyalty customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. *Store atmosphere* makes an impact of 14.0% against loyalty customer. Coefficient track marked positive indicates that it is getting more interesting *store atmosphere* will make loyalty customer *Coffee Shop Garut's copyology* is getting higher . Research result This in line with research previously done _ (Baharuddin & Sudaryanto, 2021) which is carried out on consumers Semarang *coffee shop with* a sample of 100 respondents taken using method *non-probability sampling*, results This research shows that *store atmosphere* has an influence significant to loyalty customer of 0.153 or 15.3%.

Influence Sales Promotion to Loyalty Customer

Promotion sale is activities carried out with a purpose for provide various incentive to use increase interesting attention consumers and improve sale for company. Form indicated incentives _ to consumer form coupons, discounts prices, demonstrations, prizes and so on.

Analysis results path shows that *sales promotion* influential significant to loyalty customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. *Sales promotion* exert influence of 13.1% against loyalty customer. Coefficient track marked positive indicates that it is getting more interesting *sales promotion* will make loyalty customer *Coffee Shop Garut's copyology* is getting higher . Research result This in line with research previously done _ (Hutabarat & Prabawani, 2020) Hutabarat and Prabawani (2020) states that the variable *sales promotion* have influence significant and positive to loyalty customer amounting to 34.8%. Furthermore research

conducted by (Nurwulandri & Maharani, 2021) conducted at COFEE19 *café*, the results of the research revealed that promotions had a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty of 0.492 or 49.2%.

The Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Satisfaction customer is one of factor important thing to do noticed company. So company must endeavor to provide benefits products and services that suit your needs consumer. If benefits provided _ exceed hope consumer then consumer will feel satisfied, on the contrary if No according to expectations consumers will feel disappointed. _ If consumer own level high satisfaction _ to something goods or services, this is next will increase loyalty consumer.

Analysis results path shows that satisfaction customer influential significant to loyalty customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology*. Satisfaction customer exert influence amounting to 48.9% against loyalty customer. Coefficient track marked positive indicates that it is getting higher satisfaction customer will make loyalty customers at *the Coffee Shop Garut Copyology* the higher it is. Research result This in line with research previously done (Saputra & Margaretha, 2020) conducted at *Coffee Bean & Tea Leaf or Maxx Coffee* , research This tested 150 customers with results showing satisfaction customer influential significant to loyalty customer amounting to 51.1%. Furthermore research conducted by (Jannah & Haanurat, 2019) stated that satisfaction consumer influential positive significant to loyalty customer amounting to 49.1%.

CONCLUSION

- (1) *store atmosphere* on Kopilogy not enough interesting with a low value on the indicator not enough interesting in preparation distance between table , *exterior design* , room Still not enough well organized , caused placement goods Still not enough well organized
- (2) *sales promotion* are in the category not enough interesting with a low value on the indicator *discounts* held _ Still not enough interesting because not enough varies .
- (3) Satisfaction customers on Kopilogy are in the category not enough satisfied with the value low on indicators design and promotion sale Not yet according to expectations.
- (4) Loyalty customer Copyology on categories not enough Attractive with value low on indicators not enough interested for visit return after first purchase.
- (5) *Store atmosphere* and *sales promotions* have an influence to satisfaction customer. *sales promotion* has influence more dominant to satisfaction .
- (6) *Store atmosphere*, *sales promotion*, satisfaction customer influential to loyalty customer of 76.0%, the better *the Store atmosphere* and *sales promotion* then satisfaction increases and forms loyalty.

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